

Original Research Article

ENTERPRISE INFORMATION SYSTEM: UPSHOT FOR ADMINISTRATIVE EFFICIENCY OF LOCAL CONSTRUCTION FIRMS

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ABSTRACT: The study probed into the relationship between enterprise information systems and the administrative efficiency of local construction firms in Rivers State. The study dimension was cloud-based EIS; while cost minimization and real-time optimization measured the dependent variable. The research provided answers to two questions and tested two hypotheses to establish the hypothesis formulation that there is no significant relationship between enterprise information systems and administrative efficiency. The study population comprised of twenty-four Local construction firms in Rivers State. The research selected three managerial staff members from each of the firms under study making it a total of seventy-two study elements. Data were generated from the respondents by the use of a well-structured questionnaire. Pearson’s product-moment correlation was used to test hypotheses with the aid of statistical packages for social science (SPSS) version 23.0. The p-values were calculated to determine the significance of the hypothesized relationship. Analytical outcomes revealed statistically positive and significant relationships between the dimensions of our predictor variable-enterprise information system and the measures of the criterion variable-administrative efficiency. Based on the findings, the study concluded that enterprise information system has a positive significant relationship with administrative efficiency of Local construction firms in Rivers State. The study further recommended amongst others, that Managers of local construction firms should apply objectivity in their Hybrid EIS processes as this has the potency to either ruin or enhance their Administrative Efficiency.

Keywords: Enterprise Information System, Administration, EIS, AE, Information, Construction, Efficiency

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INTRODUCTION

Today, our organizations face technological innovations and interventions that overwhelm their processes and operations. These innovations provide the dynamism you need to keep up with the trends of the times while increasing efficiency in all areas of your business. Enterprise information systems are part of a technology competency tree that provides tools to help

companies stand the test of time and operate as efficiently as possible. An enterprise information system (EIS) is a business management system that includes a comprehensive and integrated set of software that, when properly implemented, can be used to manage and integrate all business functions within an organization. These sets typically include a set of advanced business applications and tools for finance and costing, sales and distribution, materials management, human resources, production planning and computer-integrated manufacturing, supply chain, and customer information (Boykin, 2001; Chen, 2001; Yen et al., 2002). These packages can facilitate the flow of information between all supply chain processes (internal and external) within an organization (Al-Mashari & Zairi, 2000a).

Additionally, EIS systems can be used as a tool to improve the performance level of supply chain networks by helping to reduce cycle times (Gardiner et al., 2002). However, they are traditionally used in capital-intensive industries such as manufacturing, construction, aerospace, and defence. Recent literature has expanded EIS systems beyond manufacturing to include finance, healthcare, hotel chains, education, insurance, retail, and telecommunications. EIS is currently considered an entry-level price point for running a business and, at least for now, an entry-level price point for connecting other businesses in the network economy and enabling e-commerce between businesses (Boykin, 2001).

Moreover, many multinational companies limit their business to companies that use the same EIS software as the multinational company. The fact is that EIS is designed for large enterprises, and small and medium-sized enterprises must adapt their business models and approaches to the practices and software of large enterprises. Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) face major challenges in opening up the economy. Lacking the robustness of large enterprises, small businesses must harness the power of IT and integrated information systems to remain competitive and customer-focused. EIS is often seen as the answer to survival (Rao, 2000). This makes the EIS software market one of the largest IT investments in the world today.

Suffice it to say that EIS packages affect many aspects of a company's internal and external operations. Therefore, the successful implementation and use of EIS systems are critical to organizational performance and survival (Markus et al., 2000b). Potential benefits include dramatic inventory reductions, breakthrough working capital savings, comprehensive information about customer wants and needs, and increased enterprise size for suppliers, partnerships, and customers. It includes functions that can be viewed and managed as a whole (Chen, 2001). In manufacturing industries, the implementation of EIS has reduced inventory levels by 15 to 35 per cent (Gupta, 2000). EIS allows companies, especially domestic oil and gas producers, to consolidate sector information. It has evolved from an HR application to an all-encompassing tool for IT management. For many users, an EIS is a comprehensive system that covers everything from order entry to customer service. Strive to integrate suppliers and customers into your organization's manufacturing environment.

For example, when a purchase is entered in the Orders module; that order is routed to the Manufacturing application, which then sends a material request to the Supply Chain module. The supply chain module receives the required parts from suppliers and transports them using the logistics module to the factory. At the same time, purchase transactions are typically reported as sales in the general ledger module. Traditional application systems commonly used in enterprises process each transaction individually. These are based on strong restrictions on the specific functionality that a particular application is intended to perform. EIS no longer treats

these transactions as independent activities but as part of the interconnected processes that make up the company (Gupta, 2000). The benefits of his EIS implementation in a local construction company in Rivers State, Nigeria is that it can help manage the business while supporting automation and processes in manufacturing, finance, human resources, and other organizational aspects at different generations and developments. It extends to. In light of the above, this study examines how EIS provides an organization of local construction companies in Rivers State, Nigeria with the resources it needs to run its business and support to fully automate its processes and practices and will consider whether it is possible.

Statement of the Problem

The indigenous construction sector in Rivers State, Nigeria, has long struggled with inefficiencies and mismanagement due to inadequate standardization and automation of processes and operations. As overtime hours accumulate, these challenges compromise a company's growth, sustainability, and ultimately, its survival. This research aims to address this persistent issue through the implementation of Enterprise Information Systems (EIS), recognizing that effective stakeholder management is crucial for achieving operational efficiency and a resilient organizational structure. Previous studies have highlighted the significance of EIS in optimizing organizational processes and productivity. The construction industry's unique characteristics, such as project-based operations and diverse stakeholder interests, exacerbate the need for streamlined processes and efficient resource allocation. This study investigates the relationship between EIS and administrative efficiency in local construction firms in Rivers State, Nigeria, with a focus on overcoming the challenges of resource inefficiency, mismanagement, and stagnant growth.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study aim to examine how an enterprise information system is an upshot for the administrative efficiency of local construction firms. The specific objectives are to:

- Determine the relationship between cloud-based EIS and cost minimization in local construction firms in Rivers State, and
- Investigate the relationship between cloud-based EIS and real-time optimization in local construction firms in Rivers State.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and statistically tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

- **H₀₁**: There is no significant relationship between cloud-based EIS and cost minimization in local construction firms in Rivers State.
- **H₀₂**: There is no significant relationship between cloud-based EIS and real-time optimization in local construction firms in Rivers State.

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

Enterprise Information System (EIS)

An enterprise information system is a business management system with integrated software that, when fully implemented, can be used to manage and coordinate all business activities within an organization. These collections often include business processes as well as financial and costing tools, sales and distribution, materials management, human resources, production planning and computer-aided manufacturing, supply chain, and customer information (Boykin, 2001; Chen, 2001; Yan et al., 2002). These packages facilitate the flow of information between all channels (internal and external) within an organization (Al-Mashari & Zairi, 2000a). Also, the management of technical information (data such as materials, planning processes, office information, etc.) between different types of EIS; Sales, acquisition and inventory; Material requirements planning (MRP); program management (production, financial management, human resources); work documentation (work orders, warehouse orders, product and assembly release documents); Land management and administration, cost management, transportation, information system maintenance, etc. The EIS model also covers areas such as finance (financial accounting, financial management, corporate governance, asset management), logistics (production planning, material management, equipment maintenance, quality control, project structure, sales), and human resources management. This includes training and development (capability inventory) and workflow (organization-wide integration of flexible allocation of tasks and responsibilities to locations, positions, jobs, groups or individuals) (Siriginidi, 2000).

Administrative Efficiency

The word "efficiency" is different from the word "effectiveness." However, both are used to explain the workings of place (Chinyere & Ikoromasoma, 2021). This means that efficiency focuses on producing the best results with the least number of ideas; optimising the use of resources and producing the best products at the lowest prices. Irsova (2010) stated that by supporting macroeconomic policy outcomes, efficiency leads to growth, economic development, and human well-being. This is in line with McKnley and Banaian (2000), who argued that efficiency includes costs and profits because base maximization and profit maximization are part of the definition of efficiency. The use of the term "administration" is so widespread that its meaning and concept are ignored. This is because the word is currently used in a variety of ways and its meaning appears to be related to the context in which it is used (Bestman, 2020).

Administration refers to the management process or executive function in a business, organization, etc. In this study, the researchers define administration as the process or activity of managing an enterprise, especially with the help of resources. Under planning, it is like everyone in business is managing this or that. Therefore, rules apply to administration. These policies may be formal or informal. Organizational efficiency refers to an organization's success in achieving maximum results with minimum inputs. Efficiency is defined as the highest level of productivity that produces maximum output with minimum input. Efficiency is a term that has recently gained prominence in the scientific community. As the world struggles to adapt to population growth and manage resource allocation, efforts to improve efficiency are critical (Chinyere & Ikuromasoma, 2021).

Efficiency as the ratio of output units to input units. A firm is likely to be more efficient than other firms if it can use inputs to produce more output than other firms. Similarly, Mardas (2004) added that administrative efficiency refers to budgeting, i.e. the ratio of administrative expenditure to total expenditure. It is therefore clear that the for-profit public sector is a means of making public service delivery more efficient and increasing the value of public funds. Identifying and valuing public goods and services (i.e., measuring their efficiency) is often a difficult task. This is mainly because the impact (output) is both direct and therefore undefinable, and also indirect due to the reliability and clarity of the external substances and purposes that produce it (Mihaiu et al., 2015).

Cloud-based EIS

Information technology uses new information to solve business problems. Cloud computing is a new form of IT delivery; It is a new way of using network equipment to provide various IT needs to different customers with a single payment (Plummer, 2008). Cloud computing is "a model that provides widespread, convenient, on-demand network access to a shared organization of computing resources (such as networks, servers, storage, applications, and services) that can be quickly deployed and released, or manage interactions between service providers" (Mell & Gance, 2011). Cloud-based solutions because copying delays and users can easily buy more electronic products at low cost (Wu et al., 2011). Through Cloud service, organizations can reduce the total IT cost by moving IT functions such as storage, marketing, etc. (Goscinski & Brock, 2010; Stanoevska-Slabeva et al., 2009). Therefore, cloud computing has provided businesses with commercial benefits that cannot be ignored. The on-demand and pay-as-you-go requirements of cloud computing mean that there is no need to pay if the service is not used.

The general service of cloud computing refers to the services provided by cloud computing. Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) refers to the provision of computing power and on-demand storage provided by well-structured, often virtualized infrastructure and automated system management (Wang et al., 2010). Second, Platform as a Service (PaaS) describes the development and running platform, operating, testing and management environment provided as a service or option. Third: Data as a Service (DaaS): Internet users can access data from different sources and in different formats through services. For example, the user can remotely update files or access files on the network while working on the local hard disk (Wang et al., 2010). Storage as a Service (DaaS) is also known as DaaS in many places (Wu et al., 2010). Finally, Software as a Service (SaaS) is a collaborative software offering that encompasses all major IT resources (infrastructure, management, maintenance) with Internet and network connectivity. It can be taken from "units" and given as "units". Use "basic units".

Cost Minimization

The emphasis is on cost reduction and continuous improvement and change rather than cost containment. Instead of the term "cost optimization," the term "cost reduction" may be used. While traditional cost management systems are used daily, cost optimization is typically used on a one-time basis when cost-saving opportunities are identified. Cost minimization is the action taken by managers to reduce costs. Some of these actions are prioritized based on information from your accounting system. Cost optimization aims to reduce costs, but not at the expense of customer satisfaction. Ideally, you want to take steps to reduce costs and increase customer

satisfaction. Minimizing costs is a pivot in today's competitive business environment. The purpose of this study was to define cost optimization and discuss the basic optimization philosophy. There have been clear changes in cost and operations accounting over the past 25 years (Lin, 2022). These changes are the result of an increasingly competitive environment due to the introduction of new production and information technologies, customer focus, growth of global markets and the introduction of new forms of management organization (Huang & Wang, 2017).

In terms of cost minimization, we are interested in cash costs, which are an indicator of the efficiency of a company's performance. Costs are the sum of factors of production and production activities. There is no doubt that every organization seeks to minimize costs to maximize profits. This is achieved through concepts such as affordability and cost savings. Several cost concepts appear in the discussion of profit planning and management but are limited here to three. These are quality, labour and strategic costs. Any business that wants to survive and feed its customers must work to improve its products. Therefore, organizations must ensure that their operations are as efficient as possible to avoid going over budget, incurring losses, or deteriorating product quality (Chinyere & Ikoromasoma, 2021). Domestic construction firms face low profitability and high compliance investments that require constant vigilance and cost control. Domestic construction firms in Nigeria's Rivers State are now in dire need of finding ways to be more efficient.

Cost savings in this industry can only be achieved if operational activities and processes become more efficient (Nwinyokpugi & Alikornwo, 2022). In this study, the essence of enterprise information systems revolves around promoting efficiency, reducing costs and maximising company profits. Thus, domestic construction firms can achieve organizational efficiency through the implementation of enterprise information systems. Therefore, to maintain high profitability in an ever-competitive global economy, construction firms companies need to adopt appropriate techniques and measures to keep up with the times (Nwinyokpugi & Alikornwo, 2022).

Real-time Optimization

Real-time optimization is the actual time a process or event occurs at the expected time. It is also the process of achieving a specified goal or result within an expected period. Efficiency of operational activities and processes in the domestic construction sector improves speed, on-time delivery, and many other process indicators. True organizational efficiency minimizes the waste of resources, such as labour time, while achieving desired results. Real-time services can only be achieved in inefficiently managed organizations (Chinyere & Ikuromasoma, 2021). Real-time services are made possible by keeping the employees of the Rivers State domestic construction firms informed of internal and external operational information to maximize the company's resource planning. Organizational stakeholders monitor the company's operations. Real-time services allow you to monitor success recorded at every critical point. This helps managers and decision-makers track the successes and failures of their subordinates.

This means key stakeholders do not have to carry around documents to get the knowledge they need to do their jobs, and they have free access to the information they need. The business of local construction companies is very diverse and complex. Many of our services are provided jointly or independently. Responding to customer needs by improving the efficiency of the domestic construction sector becomes a key strategy to achieve better customer loyalty and

achieve organizational and institutional efficiency. With so many choices available to customers, customer demands may be higher than ever, and businesses must be able to track, predict, and respond to changing customer preferences promptly. Therefore, it must be said that real-time services capture the efficiency level of employees of domestic construction firms that provide value-added services (Nwinyokpugi & Alikornwo, 2022).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theoretical foundation of this work is hinged on the General Systems Theory.

General Systems Theory

General systems theory is the backbone of science in the sense that it aims to provide a system framework or structure that can organize the flesh and blood of a particular field or subject area into an orderly and coherent body of knowledge (Boulding, 1956). Systems theory, originally derived from biology, was developed in the 1950s against the backdrop of the need for a systematic set of theoretical constructs to discuss the empirical world (Boulding, 1956; von Bertalanffy, 1951). Another origin of systems theory is in cybernetic systems theory in mechanical engineering (Ashby, 1954; Wiener, 1948). Organizations and systems have evolved many times over the years, inevitably becoming more complex. Recent studies have shown that systems approaches to studying organizations are becoming increasingly popular. With the advent of globalization and the information age, researchers have found that systems approaches can help understand organizations in these new and changing environments. Revolutionary advances in communication technology have enabled companies to outsource at lower costs and better respond to environmental changes (Lai & Lin, 2017).

With the increasing adoption of information and communication technologies within and outside of organizational environments, the realm of interaction has become fluid and ambiguous, increasing the complexity of both organizations and the environments in which they are embedded (Yoon & Kuchinke, 2005). Many researchers have applied systems theory to the study of complex networks and organizations (how they interact with large numbers of stakeholders). Manage large amounts of data, information, and knowledge and improve organizations through digital feedback and control mechanisms (Lai & Lin, 2017). Considering the above, it is enough to assume that technology is the basis of innovation. Therefore, it has benefited enterprise information systems and administrative efficiency. This study conceptualized the following framework as a guide through the study.

Figure 1: Framework of enterprise information system and administrative efficiency of local construction firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

This study is descriptive as such adopted a cross-sectional survey design suitable for this study. The study population comprised twenty-four local construction firms operating in Rivers State. The researchers considered three (3) managers of each of the Local construction firms in Rivers State as the target population. The respondents/elements of this study were limited to the top, senior, and junior managers of each of the local construction firms in Rivers State. Thus, 72 copies of the structured close-ended 4-point Likert scale questionnaire were administered to the categories of employees that formed the respondents mainly Top and Senior Managerial Cadres. The reliability test of the structured questionnaires was ascertained through a Test-re-test in which a pilot administration of the questionnaire was made on a portion of the chosen sample and administered after two months and the relationship between the two results was determined by a correlation coefficient. Our reliability test was also anchored on the Cronbach Alpha at .70. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was employed at the secondary level of analysis, to test the hypothesized statements at a .05 level of significance. All the statistical analyses were performed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0.; because this version can transform scaled data into discrete or continued data and vice versa.

Decision Rule

Reject H_0 if $PV < 0.05$

Accept H_0 if $PV > 0.05$

Table 1 Showing Strength and Direction of Relationship between Variables

Range of values	Degree of relationship
$\pm 0.00 - \pm 0.19$	Very weak
$\pm 0.20 - \pm 0.39$	Weak
$\pm 0.40 - \pm 0.59$	Moderate
$\pm 0.60 - \pm 0.79$	Strong
$\pm 0.80 - \pm 1.00$	Very strong

TEST OF HYPOTHESES

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between cloud-based EIS and cost minimization in local construction firms in Rivers State

Table 2 Relationship between Cloud-based EIS and Cost minimization

		Cloud-based EIS	Cost minimization
Cloud-based EIS	Pearson Correlation	1	.692**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	53	53
Cost minimization	Pearson Correlation	.692**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	53	53

** . Correlation is significant at the .001 level (2-tailed).

From Table 2 analysis, it can be observed that there is a correlation coefficient of .692** between Cloud-based EIS and cost minimization, indicating a strong and positive relationship between Cloud-based EIS and cost minimization. More so, the probability value (.000) is less than the critical value (.05), this shows that there is a strong significant relationship between Cloud-based EIS and cost minimization. This further implies that most of the changes in cost minimization among local construction firms in Rivers State are caused by their Cloud-based EIS while others are caused by externalities. Based on this, we reject the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Cloud-based EIS and cost minimization of local construction firms and incline to the alternate hypothesis that there is a strong, significant relationship between cloud-based EIS and cost minimization of local construction firms.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between cloud-based EIS and real-time optimization in local construction firms in Rivers State

Table 3 Relationship between Cloud-based EIS and Real-time optimization

		Cloud-based EIS	Real-time optimization
Cloud-based EIS	Pearson Correlation	1	.679**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	53	53
Real-time optimization	Pearson Correlation	.679**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	53	53

** . Correlation is significant at the .001 level (2-tailed).

From Table 3 analysis, it can be observed that there is a Correlation coefficient of .679** between Cloud-based EIS and real-time optimization, indicating a strong and positive relationship between Cloud-based EIS and improved decision-making. More so, the probability value (.000) is less than the critical value (.05), this shows that there is a strong significant relationship between Cloud-based EIS and real-time optimization. This further implies that most of the real-time optimization experienced among local construction firms in Rivers State is caused by their Cloud-based EIS while others are caused by externalities. Based on this, we reject the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Cloud-based EIS and real-time optimization of local construction firms and incline to the alternate hypothesis that there is a strong, significant relationship between cloud-based EIS and real-time optimization of local construction firms.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Cloud-based EIS and Cost Minimization

The study revealed a strong and positive relationship between cloud-based Enterprise Information Systems (EIS) and cost minimization, with a correlation coefficient of .692** (p-value = .000 < .05). This indicates that the implementation of cloud-based EIS significantly contributes to cost reduction.

Cloud-based EIS and Real-time Optimization

The study also found a strong and positive relationship between cloud-based EIS and real-time optimization, with a correlation coefficient of .679** (p-value = .000 < .05). This suggests that cloud-based EIS significantly enhances real-time optimization capabilities. These findings support existing literature, including Nizar (2021), which highlighted the benefits of cloud-based EIS in cost reduction, profitability, and organizational control.

CONCLUSION

In line with the findings of this study and to the extent of its consistency with results of similar previous studies, we conclude that enterprise information system has a positive significant relationship with Administrative Efficiency of local construction firms in Rivers State. Thus, an enterprise information system is a key imperative for cost minimization and improvement in Administrative Efficiency within the Rivers State construction sector given its cloud-based EIS, which in turn impacts cost minimization of the business, as well as real-time optimization of the firm.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study and the extent of its consistency with the results of similar studies we make the following recommendation.

- Managers of local construction firms should capitalize on the pivot role of cloud-based EIS in their operations to ensure their Administrative Efficiency.
- Managers of local construction firms should adopt the avalanche remedies offered through enterprise information systems, as it is seen to positively influence administrative efficiency.

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